

Mapping quantum harmonic oscillator of Hydrogen atom into electron relativistic kinetic energy,

Agnius Vasiliauskas, 2024

Abstract

In this paper I try to relate Hydrogen atom's electron relativistic energy to standard quantum harmonic oscillator ground state, intermediately using semi-classical Bohr atom model properties like electron tangential speed in Hydrogen atom. This should give new insights into fine-structure constant α and ways to calculate quantum harmonic oscillator ground state energy from purely relativistic perspective.

Classically from the nature of electron centripetal force being Coulomb electrostatic force in Hydrogen atom one can derive tangential speed of electron in a ground state which is,

$$v = \sqrt{\frac{k_e e^2}{m_e r_b}} \approx \alpha c \quad (1)$$

Where r_b is Bohr radius. From here follows basic interpretation of fine-structure constant $\alpha = v/c$, - it's electron speed in a ground state of Hydrogen atom in terms of c factor. Electron relativistic kinetic energy in a Hydrogen atom is,

$$K_{rel} = \frac{m_e}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} c^2 - m_e c^2 \quad (2)$$

Using ansatz that (2) is in the form of $\beta m_e c^2$ and electron speed in a ground state Hydrogen (1), one can find the form of β coefficient which is,

$$\beta = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \alpha^2}} - 1 \quad (3)$$

Since α is very small, ≈ 0.0073 we can expand (3) into Taylor series about zero point, which would be ,

$$\beta = \frac{\alpha^2}{2} + \frac{3\alpha^4}{8} + \frac{5\alpha^6}{16} + \frac{35\alpha^8}{128} + \dots \quad (4)$$

Taking only first term of (4) as good enough approximation and substituting it into Hydrogen atom at ground state level ansatz $\beta m_e c^2$, one arrives at

$$K_{rel} = \frac{1}{2} \alpha^2 m_e c^2 \quad (5)$$

,i.e. electron relativistic ground state kinetic energy. Now if we assume that the only source of Hydrogen atom ground state quantum harmonic oscillator energy is from contribution of relativistic kinetic energy of electron, i.e. that ,

$$E_0 = \frac{\hbar\omega}{2} = K_{rel} \quad (6)$$

then using (5) we can get very important α^2 interpretation, which is :

$$\alpha^2 = \frac{\hbar\omega}{m_e c^2} \quad (7)$$

, that is,- it is the ratio of Hydrogen atom ground state oscillator double-energy to the electron mass-energy.

Conclusions

Using classic definition of electron speed in a ground state of Hydrogen atom and employing relativistic kinetic energy concept,- I have derived approximation of electron relativistic kinetic energy in a Hydrogen ground state (5). Mapping this electron relativistic kinetic energy to the quantum harmonic oscillator ground state energy let us to define new interpretation of α^2 expressed in (7). This is very important since it connects special relativity and quantum mechanics, i.e. mass-energy with quantum oscillator energy. As a side-effect one can deduce classical electron rotation frequency around Hydrogen atom nuclei at a ground state from (7) expression, which would give staggering 10^{16} Hz order frequency in peta-Hertz domain.